

Soil is a sandy loam (Typic Ustochrepts), with pH 7.3, low organic matter, 0.29% organic C in the top 0-15 cm layer, and no hardpan for 2 m.

Treatments included green manuring (GM) with *Sesbania aculeata*, summer mung *Vigna radiata*, and mixing farmyard manure (FYM) in soil before transplanting rice. Average dry biomass added to soil per yr was 5.2 t sesbania/ha, 3.4 t summer mung/ha, and 4.0 t FYM/ha.

We added 90-13-25 kg NPK/ha to the sesbania, summer mung, and FYM treatments during the rice crop and 120-13-25 kg NPK/ha to the fallow treatment.

In the following wheat crop, 120-26-50 kg NPK/ha was added in all the treatments.

We took undisturbed soil cores every 5 cm, up to a depth of 30 cm, for the bulk density measurements, used double ring infiltrometers to measure infiltration, and used wet sieving to estimate the water-stable aggregates.

Application of FYM did not affect soil bulk density (see table). Green manuring with summer mung, up to 10 cm, and sesbania, up to 20 cm, showed significant decreases in bulk density compared with the fallow; maximum decrease was with

sesbania GM, irrespective of depth.

The infiltration rate did not differ between fallow and FYM treatments (see figure), but it increased significantly over the fallow treatment with summer mung and sesbania GM. Water-stable aggregates larger than 2 mm were significantly more in FYM treatment; those of smaller size (<0.5 mm) were significantly more in the sesbania treatment (see table).

Continuous application of GM improves the physical properties of soils in a rice - wheat system where soil is puddled before rice is transplanted. □

Crop management

Farmer-participatory rainfed lowland rice varietal testing in Cambodia

R. C. Chaudhary, Cambodia-IRRI Project; and S. Fujisaku, IRRI

Farmer-participatory varietal testing ideally helps to identify superior varieties grown under farmers' conditions and management, draws farmer feedback regarding varietal characteristics, provides a mechanism for seed multiplication of farmer-desired varieties, and serves as demonstration for nonparticipating farmers.

Replicated yield trials conducted by the Cambodia-IRRI Project showed rice varieties IR66, IR72, and Kru as promising for the rainfed lowlands of Cambodia. Government and nongovernment organizations then distributed seed from on-farm adaptive trials to farmers throughout the country. Methods and goals of the planned farmer-participatory trials were explained to potential cooperators. Interested farmers tested the rice varieties alongside their own cultivars, using their own inputs and management practices. No guarantees were given to cooperators for any crop losses,

Trials in the 1990 wet season (WS) and the 1991 dry season (DS) were on 100-m² plots (5 × 20 m) located where hers in the community could easily observe results. Participating farmers

(75 for WS and 39 for DS) provided data on seeding and transplanting dates, fertilizer use, crop problems, yields, and farmer evaluations of the introduced rice varieties. Field days were conducted prior to harvest.

The three introduced varieties and the local checks (most commonly IR36 and IR64, or a few local cultivars) did not significantly differ in yield in both WS and DS. Yields were significantly higher when any amount of fertilizer was applied than when none was applied (Table 1). As expected, DS yields were higher than WS yields. More farmers (49%) applied fertilizer in DS than in WS (31%). Regression of yields for the varieties showed no difference in responsiveness to fertilizers. This was expected because the introduced and almost all of the varieties were IRRI varieties or lines (Kru).

Varieties were also ranked by yield per farm. IR66 was the highest yielder the most times in both WS and DS and the lowest yielder the fewest times. Kru was the highest yielder the fewest times. Farmers' varieties were the lowest yielders the most times (Table 2). These results indicate that IR66 and IR72 have greater yield stability over different locations than Kru and farmers' varieties,

Most farmers did not provide evaluations of the tested varieties. They appeared to be optimizing production of their current varieties. Perhaps as a result of this, they had relatively little to offer in terms of evaluation, either negative or positive. The project offered to buy back

seed produced from the three varieties, but none of the farmers were interested in selling. We observed, however, that seed from the new varieties was being disseminated from farmer to farmer. The apparent greater stability of IR66 and IR72 was expected to be attractive to farmers.

In the short run, constraints to farmers' use of fertilizers need to be further examined. Farmers not currently using any would clearly increase their yields by using fertilizer. □

Table 1. Yields of introduced and farmers' rainfed lowland rice varieties grown with and without fertilizer. Cambodia, 1990 WS and 1991 DS.

Variety	Yield ^a (t/ha)			
	1990 WS		1991 DS	
	With fertilizer (n = 23)	Without fertilizer (n = 52)	With fertilizer (n = 19)	Without fertilizer (n = 20)
IR66	3.5	2.1	5.5	3.9
IR72	3.1	2.1	4.9	4.2
KRU	3.0	2.5	5.0	3.6
Farmers'	3.0	2.1	4.3	4.1

^a Test of means between fertilizer treatments using *t*-test was significant at 1% for both seasons. Test of means among varieties using DMRT was nonsignificant.

Table 2. Frequency that each introduced and farmer rainfed lowland rice variety ranked first through fourth for yield. Cambodia, 1990 WS and 1991 DS.

Variety	1990 WS				1991 DS			
	1	2	3	4	1	2	3	4
IR66	34	18	17	4	17	10	8	2
IR72	24	21	23	5	13	8	11	3
KRU	6	32	20	15	3	16	10	7
Farmers'	15	18	21	19	10	7	8	13